

USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The purpose of teaching foreign languages with innovative teaching methods and new technological processes is not only to impart knowledge and develop speech skills to students, but also to stimulate their interest in learning foreign languages, to harness their internal potential, and to build their confidence in their own abilities.

Key words: English language, interactive methods, independent language learning, knowledge, skills, “studies”.

Modern conditions demand not only the use of new technologies in teaching foreign languages, but also the implementation of innovative changes in teaching methodology and the introduction of the latest innovative technologies in the process of learning foreign languages. The most effective methods of teaching that focus on the independence, adaptability, and critical thinking of students are preferred. The most powerful source of student creativity, interests, skills, and other mental abilities is these innovative technologies. Innovative educational technologies are primarily information and communication technologies related to computerized education. The main challenges of using innovative technologies include the content of computerized education programs, their substance, and the proper organization of the Web environment.

Over the years, various subjects, theories, and teaching methods have been developed for teaching foreign languages. You cannot find the best, unique, and quick method for teaching English to children or adults. Choosing the right teaching method depends on the students’ interests and abilities. Therefore, there is no single method for learning English. Of course, choosing effective teaching methods depends on the teacher’s skill. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important part of professional education. People first learn such knowledge in schools, colleges, lyceums, then at institutes, training courses, or independently after getting acquainted with the basic information resources that help them learn a foreign language.

Today, there are more than twenty effective interactive methods available, most of which have passed the test and have yielded good results. The basic conditions for applying educational technologies in the learning process are as follows:

- Developing independent communication skills for each student during the teaching process;
- Using methods and modern educational tools that enhance activity in the teaching process

By the end of the 21st century, the importance of English as a global language was finally established. It became mandatory to learn it in most schools around the world and teaching methods began to evolve with restrictions and boundaries. Learning opportunities for independent development were not available to everyone. Later, many authors made efforts to create an effective program for independent learning of English, but we pay attention to the most famous 4.

1. The Shekhter method of learning English is based on a natural learning system, rather than the classic model of “from theory to practice.” This is similar to how we learn our native language. The author gives the example of how young children learn to speak – after all, no one teaches them the rules of forming sentences, situations, and parts of speech. It is in this way that Igor Yuryevich Shekhter suggests learning English. The essence of the modern method of learning English is that in the first lesson, a specific task is given to the students, for example, to learn the profession of a conversation partner. In addition, all students play “studies,” where they act in various roles and take action to solve problems. Since communication occurs between people with approximately the same level of language knowledge, there is no fear of using foreign speech in communication between teachers and students.

2. The Pimsler method was developed by Dr. Paul Pimsler not only for understanding information but also for reworking it. He created a special system of thirty-minute lessons. Each lesson is conducted by two people: our compatriot and an English speaker. With the help of special memorization technology, each student learns hundreds of words and phrases in English for each lesson. The essence of the lesson is the fulfillment of tasks presented by the audience.

3. The Dragunkin method has a distinctive feature in that any foreign language learning is oriented towards the Russian language. The author, who boldly called English an easy language, emphasizes his stars going to the ancient Russian language, especially the grammar system. Dragunkin’s course teaches students new words transcribed in Russian letters and divides grammatical constructions not into 12 tenses known to us from school, but into past, present, future, and their changes.

4. According to Petrov, it is possible to learn English in 16 hours. Indeed, the author once again points out that we are not talking about mastering the language

at the level of a native speaker, but about basic knowledge. His lessons are aimed at immersing yourself in an English-speaking environment, understanding your needs and understanding the response adequately.

Using various tables in the process of learning a foreign language is also highly effective. By using tables in the learning process, students can learn a certain grammar rule, for example, using tenses and forming sentences, placing new words. In a period when the need for learning a foreign language is high, the effective use of modern information technologies and innovative educational technologies contributes to making this process successful. The effectiveness of innovative educational technologies is realized when they are used correctly and effectively in the educational process.

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